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CHANGES OF ADAPTABILITY STRATEGIES TO PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING: A LONGITUDINAL CASE STUDY OF FIRST-YEAR CHINESE ENGINEERING GRADUATE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Problem- and project-based Learning (PBL) has been acknowledged and practiced as one of the widely accepted and innovative methods in engineering education over the last forty years at Aalborg University (AAU) in Denmark. However, the transition from lecture-based traditional learning to PBL represents a major challenge, especially for international students who have no prior knowledge and experience in PBL. In addition, more transition issues are raised by overseas students from China due to the differences in language, culture, learning styles etc. To remain and prosper in a new and competitive PBL learning environment, these engineering students must develop adaptability skills, which means that they must find ways to fit into and learn through PBL. Our previous study has identified that first-year Chinese graduate engineering students' preferred adaptability strategies are integration, assimilation and separation when adapting to PBL in their first semester at AAU. In order to enrich our understanding of adaptability as a changing process, the current longitudinal research extends the focus to the changes of the students' choice of adaptability strategies to PBL over time and aims to explore the factors which influence their selection. Four Chinese engineering graduate students were followed through consecutive semi-structured interviews during their second semester at AAU. The results indicate that both integration and separation strategies are the favored adaptability strategies at this stage. Moreover, some factors relating to PBL courses, teamwork, communication

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and language proficiency impact these Chinese engineering students' preferences for different adaptability strategies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Driven by the process of internationalization and globalization, the past years have witnessed a continuously growing number of Chinese international engineering students at Danish universities as study abroad students. Due to fundamentally different cultures and educational systems, learners from China bring with them different understandings, expectations, and ways of learning to a Danish academic environment [1]. Some previous research has shown that Chinese students are inclined to be dependent learners who get accustomed to receiving the knowledge from their teachers through lectures with limited questioning and discussions [2][3][4]. Furthermore, they rely heavily on rote and individual learning, which means that they consolidate the learning contents by memorization and repetition [2][3]. However, these learning styles and dispositions are unsuitable to educational requirements at Aalborg University (AAU) where problem- and project-based learning (PBL) are adopted [1]. In engineering education, PBL is an appealing and innovative pedagogical approach built on the basis of engineering practice. The common learning principles of this approach are featured as problem-oriented, student-centered, collaborative and active learning, self-directed teamwork, teachers as facilitators and exemplary practice [5][6]. Within the PBL frames, instead of passively reading or listening to the facts and concepts that define an academic field of study during lectures, students work together in small teams on a project that engage them in exploring real-world problems and analysing ill-structured, complex questions [7].

On account of the discrepancy between Chinese learning styles and the requirements of PBL, Chinese international students are confronted with some academic and psychological challenges when adapting to a sharply distinct PBL learning environment. Our previous study found that the challenges, which first-year Chinese engineering graduate students at AAU faced, stem from collaboration in teams, communication with groupmates, heavy academic workload and different assessment systems [8]. In addition, from the psychological perspective, these students struggle with some mental challenges including loneliness, homesickness, isolation and lack of intrinsic motivation [8]. Although these students experienced the difficulties stated above in the process of adaptation, they chose different adaptability strategies to adjust to the challenges in a new environment. In PBL context, “adaptability”, also termed “adaptation”, is defined as the extent to which engineering students are competent to fit into the new PBL educational setting by effectively shifting their previously developed knowledge, method and theory, along with modifying their thoughts, behaviors and emotions [9][10]. Inspired by Berry's acculturation theory, “adaptability strategies” refer to the various ways of adaptation among different groups of people [11]. This concept will be elaborated in detail in the theoretical framework. There is a small but growing amount of literature focusing on adaptability strategies of Chinese overseas students. However, most of it has mainly been carried out on

students integrating into traditional universities in the West [2][4][13]. Hence, it is worthwhile to enrich our understandings on Chinese first-year graduate students' adaptability strategies to PBL academic environment, particularly to investigate their changes of preferences for different strategies over time. As part of a longitudinal study, this paper seeks to address the following research questions: Compared to the first semester at AAU, what adaptability strategies do first-year Chinese engineering graduate students select during their second semester? What factors affect their selection of adaptability strategies in this stage?

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In order to answer the research questions, this study adopts Berry's theory on acculturation strategies [11]. It should be noted that the concept "acculturation" refers to the dual process of psychological adjustment in an individual as well as cultural changes in groups while the term "adaptability" or "adaptation" is one component of acculturation that emphasizes the individual change [12]. As a result, our framework uses "adaptability strategies" to explain various strategies that first-year Chinese engineering students choose in their own adaptive process to PBL. The strategies are based on two issues: (1) the extent of maintaining one's heritage culture(s) and identity and (2) the relative preference for involvement with the host culture(s) and other cultural groups. One's inclinations to these two issues determine the adaptability attitudes or strategies. Deriving from these two dimensions, four types of strategies - integration, assimilation, separation and marginalization - are proposed at the individual level. The integration strategy means that one wishes to maintain one's own cultural identity and interacts with the new society. In contrast, marginalization appears when one accepts neither home culture(s) nor host culture(s). The assimilation strategy refers to an individual that entirely participates in the dominant culture(s) while rejecting the heritage culture(s). Finally, the separation strategy occurs when one values the culture(s) of origin, but does not integrate into the dominant culture(s).

In the next sections, we will go through the methods of data collection and further investigate how these strategies apply in a real setting.

3 RESEARCH METHOD

This study is in continuity with our previous work targeting the process of adaptation but extends the focus to the changes of adaptability strategies with time. Taking the same qualitative and sequential research design in data collection as before [8], four Chinese graduate engineering students who were enrolled in the fall of 2020 were followed through the use of consecutive semi-structured interviews at their second graduate semester at AAU. By utilizing purposeful sampling [14], they were recruited because they had no prior PBL experience in their bachelor and found it challenging to transit into a PBL learning environment. Table 1 provides some basic information of the four participants. Among them, three students consented to take a face-to-face interview whereas one student engaged in an online interview. To ensure the confidentiality, all names are pseudonyms, and the identifiable data are removed.

Table 1. Description of participants

Name	Gender	Discipline	Forms of interview
Steven	Male	Electronic Engineering	Online
Ben	Male	Electronic Engineering	In person
Yvonne	Female	Electronic Engineering	In person
Joe	Male	Energy Engineering	In person

Based on Berry's adaptation strategies and our previous findings about adaptive challenges to PBL, an interview protocol was carefully designed as a guide containing several open-ended questions. Prompts from the protocol sheet centered on participants' learning activities to PBL, experiences of collaborating and communicating with the team members in a new semester, and their attitudes towards the PBL assessment system. The questions also asked them to reflect on the benefits and challenges brought by PBL at this stage, as well as to compare their own academic performance change between the two semesters at AAU. All interviews lasted approximately one hour and were conducted in Chinese so that participants were able to fully express themselves by using their native language. The first author transcribed their narrations verbatim and partially translated them into English.

With the guidance of thematic analysis [15], the entire transcripts were read through iteratively so as to get familiar with the data. Accompanying with an open-coding process, a collection of in-vivo initial codes was then identified where the students' experience may be linked to the changes of adaptability. These coded sequences were developed as an initial codebook and continued to be refined until broader and preliminary themes emerged. By analyzing and revising the themes, we further constructed new coherent and overarching categories at a conceptual level to see if they were related to the results, as well as the theoretical framework. Finally, a report was written based on the data analysis which is represented by the finalized categories.

4 FINDINGS

From these engineering students' epistemological accounts of their experiences and changes, the degree of adapting to PBL and their preferences of adaptability strategies was found to be dependent on a number of factors related to PBL courses, teamwork, communication and language proficiency. Each factor is discussed below.

4.1 Factors pertaining to PBL courses

Despite the adaptive challenges in heavy academic workload that these students encountered in the first semester, three of them reported to gradually adjust to PBL learning activities because of appropriate pre-course reading strategies, more relevant exercises, and practical mini-projects. Although Joe still lacked time in reading piles of literature before a course, he changed his ways to read. Rather than reading all references intensively, he felt at ease by mainly looking through new and unfamiliar concepts. Ben had previously held a negative attitude towards the exercises, but this semester he thought they became more meaningful and aligned with the courses. As

a result, his comprehension of what he learned got strengthened through effective application of theories. Moreover, he claimed that he valued the practical mini-projects in this term, which enhanced his interests and engagement.

“I firstly skimmed the slides from our course. The content that I already grasped were skipped so that I could primarily focus on the unknown parts. It reassured me through quickly developing a general overview of those unknown theories and their applications.” (Joe)

“We had a course where the exercises in each lecture reflected some key points of the learning content. That is to say, if I could figure out the exercise, I would totally understand what lecturers said.” ... “Unlike the last semester, the mini-project I am doing now is relatively practical. I enjoy doing it because it seems like working in a real laboratory, and meanwhile I am able to learn something new.” (Ben)

However, due to the change of research direction in their master, one student Yvonne still felt pressured by being exposed to a lot of new knowledge and faced difficulty in keeping up with the lectures.

“What I am majoring in now is quite different from my bachelor. It took me a long time to understand what I am studying.”...“The challenge also derives from my unfamiliarity with the terminologies in my field. It was hard for me to follow up on our lecturers because I needed time to self-reflect and look up those concepts online.” (Yvonne)

Under the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic, all teaching and learning activities at AAU shifted to online mode. Compared with physical courses, all four students pointed out that they integrated into studying environment online because it enabled them to schedule with more flexibility. Although they struggled with some online learning problems like procrastination and lack of concentration, the live sessions could be recorded which allowed them to review learning content at their own pace. As what Ben mentioned, recording lectures benefited him from adapting the subject to his own learning style.

“I felt very comfortable in taking courses online. In reality, I could only concentrate on studying for an hour. Therefore, I synchronously recorded the lectures into multiple one-hour sections so as to catch up with some key points of what lecturers said after the lecture.” (Ben)

4.2 Teamwork

Since PBL involves activities that appear to be only possible in teams, students must work together to organize themselves, manage a project, make own decisions, and find solutions [16]. With more chances of collaboration, three students stated that a multicultural group, balanced team roles, clear work divisions and suitable online software increased their adaptation to PBL. Joe worked with two natives and one

international student in the second graduate semester. In his opinion, this intercultural cooperation contributed to develop a certain level of openness and provide varied perspectives. Similar to Joe, in Ben's case, his group consisted of two Danish students and four PBL-entry level overseas students. From his description, flexible task arrangements and clear separation of responsibilities in his team conducted to the improvement of his collaboration skills. Steven continued to work in the same group as the previous semester. According to him, even though the project work was transferred to online this semester, the team was still managed well by using appropriate software.

“When collaborating on the project, my European group members preferred bottom-up approach while I got used to understanding the theories first. Therefore, a wider range of opinions from us guaranteed all possible angles, from both theory and application.” (Joe)

“It makes me feel more relaxed and cozier to work with some PBL beginners because we will not be constrained by a PBL framework.” ... “When a task was distributed, one of my group members firstly wrote down a draft, then I would add in new points and polish what we wrote.” (Ben)

“We selected some useful software so as to finish our distributed tasks both individually and cooperatively in different channels. We like this way to discuss our project because it would not bother the other members.” (Steven)

It is somewhat unexpected that Yvonne experienced a hard time in the teamwork. In spite of achieving a sense of belonging from her previous group members, she was surprisingly left out by them in this semester. After negotiating with her advisors and them, she decided to work on the project alone. However, as she said, she had to deal with a great deal of difficulties by herself.

“Firstly, the time to finish my project is insufficient. Furthermore, I need to learn plenty of new knowledge and at the same time make a connection of what I learned in my bachelor with that of the master. Lastly, studying from home was a challenge for me because I suffered a lot from procrastination. Right now, I am still looking for a balance between life and work.” (Yvonne)

4.3 Communication and language proficiency

PBL, as an effective approach, would encourage students' communication skills during the students' learning process [17]. Based on our qualitative data, three male students reported that the communication with their groupmates become more effective after a semester at AAU. Joe noted that his shyness prevented him from asking for help from his team members before, but presently he took more initiative to share views with them. In terms of language issues, Steven declared that low English proficiency was one of his largest challenges when adapting to PBL. Immersing himself in an English-

speaking environment, he ascribed his currently smooth conversation with groupmates at present to the improved language skill.

“At the beginning, I could not bring myself to ask many questions to my team members. When our relations got closer, I got more courageous to ask for more details.” (Joe)

“I feel my English is getting much better now than the last semester. I get used to using English to express my own opinions.” (Steven)

Moving on to Yvonne’s case, her experience of being excluded by the previous group members gave rise to some negative emotions such as anger, disappointment, sadness, helplessness and unfairness. These feelings further resulted in her reluctance to build any interpersonal relationships with the previous groupmates. Furthermore, in opposition to the other participants, language barriers remained a serious problem for her. Apart from issues like absorbing the lectures and preventing the free flow of information, it also intensified her stress on preparing oral examinations.

“I only talked with them [the previous groupmates] when doing assignments together in the courses. After finishing the lecture, I tried to avoid participating in their conversations and activities.” ... “English is still quite a big challenge for me. In my point of view, if I divide the oral evaluation into two aspects, English skills accounts for 40% while the knowledge of what we learned takes up 60%. However, compared to those English proficient speakers who only need to worry about that 60%, I also need to prepare that 40% more.” (Yvonne)

5 DISCUSSION

From our analysis of the adaptability strategies chosen by these engineering students, in comparison to their first semester at AAU, three male students leaned towards the integration strategy whereas one female student adopted the separation strategy this semester (see Table 2).

Table 2. Changes of the participants’ preference for adaptability strategies

Name	Previous adaptability strategy [8]	Adaptability strategy at present
Steven	Assimilation	Integration
Ben	Separation	Integration
Yvonne	Integration	Separation
Joe	Integration	Integration

In regard to Steven, he shifted his adaptability strategy from assimilation to integration. In the first semester, he held optimistic attitude towards PBL but relatively negative attitude towards traditional lecture-based learning in his bachelor. At this stage, he not only perceived PBL as a valuable method for enhancing his generic competencies in problem-solving, teamwork and project management, but he also began to realize

what he studied in his bachelor provided him with a solid mathematics foundation. Ben's choice of adaptability strategy was transferred into integration strategy. He was previously unwilling to build interpersonal interactions with his groupmates and acquired knowledge primarily through individual learning. This semester, nevertheless, he enjoyed both collaborative and individual learning and benefited from effective communication after working with a more multicultural group with balanced team responsibilities and concrete work division, as well as due to his successful adaptation to online courses. Joe remained committed to implementing the integration strategy. On one hand, the coordinating strategies he learned from prior learning and working experience is conducive to his cooperation with his team members. On the other hand, in this semester, he overcame more challenges in heavy academic workload, teamwork and communication. However, only Yvonne ended up with the separation strategy. The inclusive and open-minded group she worked in the first semester improved her sense of being accepted. It is worth noting that she was still looking forward to cooperating in a group, but being thrown out by her former groupmates, she now only seeks assistance from her own family and co-national peers.

6 CONCLUSION

Building upon Berry's acculturation theory, this study attempts to examine the changes in adaptability strategy choices among four first-year engineering Chinese graduate students, together with the factors that impact their selection. The qualitative data reveal that three students choose integration strategy and one select separation strategy after a period of studying in a PBL environment, which is in accordance with the results from other quantitative studies that both integration and separation are the favored adaptability strategies among overseas and first-year students [13][18]. Additionally, the outcome of the analysis shows that students' preferences for these strategies are associated with PBL courses, teamwork, communication and language proficiency. In general, the findings from this research may enrich our current understandings on transition and first-year issues towards a PBL learning context.

With empirical evidence from the engineering students, this study also highlights the needs to pay attention to the international PBL-beginners' participation in collaborative learning and their sense of belonging in an unfamiliar academic environment. We would suggest that the institutions and departments provide a more inclusive learning environment. Furthermore, it also requires school counselors and supervisors to be more concerned about the overseas students' adaptive challenges in mentality such as loneliness and isolation and provide them support in handling these problems by modelling preventive strategies and coping skills in lectures and project works. This inclusiveness in turn would lead to a greater diversity of knowledge, practice and values in the engineering field. However, only four Chinese participants are studied in this research and the small sample size makes the findings less generalizable to the larger population of Chinese international students. This limitation relates to the fact that there were only a few Chinese graduate students enrolled at AAU in the fall of 2020 due to COVID-19 pandemic. But the small number of students make it possible

to have a more in-depth study of their reasons for choice of strategy. For the future work, it leaves room for exploring adaptability issues in a larger sample which include more Chinese students and more international students from different nations as well.

REFERENCES

- [1] Gram, M., Jæger, K., Liu, J., Qing, L., and Wu, X. (2013), Chinese students making sense of problem-based learning and Western teaching - pitfalls and coping strategies, *Teaching in Higher Education*, Vol. 18, No. 7, pp. 761-772.
- [2] Wang, T., and Moore, L. (2007), Exploring Learning Style Preferences of Chinese Postgraduate Students in Australian Transnational Programs. *International Journal of Pedagogies and Learning*, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 31-41.
- [3] Sit, H. H. W. (2013), Characteristics of Chinese students' learning styles, *International proceedings of economics development and research*, Vol. 62, pp. 36-39.
- [4] Chen, R. T. H., Bennett, S., and Maton, K. (2008), The adaptation of Chinese international students to online flexible learning: Two case studies, *Distance Education*, Vol. 29, No. 3, pp. 307-323.
- [5] De Graaff, E., and Kolmos, A (2003), Characteristics of Problem-Based Learning, *International Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 19, No. 5, pp. 657-662.
- [6] Kolmos, A., De Graaff, E., and Du, X. (2009), Diversity of PBL-PBL learning principles and models, *Research on PBL Practice in Engineering Education*, Sense Publishers, Rotterdam, pp. 9-21.
- [7] Kolmos, A., Fink, F. K., and Krogh, L. (2004), The Aalborg model: problem-based and project-organized learning, In A. Kolmos, F. K. Fink and L. Krogh (Eds.), *The Aalborg model: progress, diversity and challenges*, Aalborg University Press, Aalborg, pp. 9-18.
- [8] Jiang, D., Dahl, B., & Bøgelund, P. (2021). Adaptability to Problem-based Learning at Aalborg University: Experience from four first-year Chinese engineering graduate students. In A. Guerra, J. Chen, M. Winther, A. Kolmos, & S. R. Nielsen (Eds.), *Educate for the future: PBL, Sustainability and Digitalisation 2021*, pp. 131-140.
- [9] Sirotiak, T., and Sharma, A. (2019), Problem-Based Learning for Adaptability and Management Skills. *Journal of Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice*, Vol. 145, No. 4.

- [10] Collie, R. J., Holliman, A. J., and Martin, A. J (2017), Adaptability, engagement and academic achievement at university. *Educational Psychology*, Vol. 37, No. 5, pp. 632-647.
- [11] Berry, J. W. (2016). Theories and models of acculturation, In the Oxford Handbook of Acculturation and Health, Oxford University Press, Oxford, pp. 15–28.
- [12] Berry, J. W. (2005). Acculturation: Living successfully in two cultures. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, Vol. 29, 6 SPEC. ISS., pp. 697–712.
- [13] Yu, W., and Wang, S. (2011). An Investigation into the Acculturation Strategies Of Chinese Students in Germany. *Intercultural Communication Studies*, Vol.20, No. 2, pp. 190–210.
- [14] Creswell, J. W. (2012). Collecting Qualitative Data, Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research. Pearson Education. Boston. pp. 206-209.
- [15] Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2012). Thematic analysis, APA Handbook of Research Methods in Psychology. APA Handbook of Research Methods in Psychology, Vol 2: Research Designs: Quantitative, Qualitative, Neuropsychological, and Biological. pp. 57-71.
- [16] Alves, A. C., Mesquita, D., Moreira, F., and Fernandes, S. (2012). Teamwork in Project-Based learning: engineering students' perceptions of strengths and weaknesses. In *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE2012)*, São Paulo, pp. 23–32.
- [17] Awang, H., and Daud, Z. (2015). Improving a Communication Skill Through the Learning Approach Towards the Environment of Engineering Classroom. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Vol. 195, pp. 480-486.
- [18] Ulriksen, L., Madsen, L. M., and Holmegaard, H. T. (2017). The first-year experience of non-traditional students in Danish science and engineering university programmes. *European Educational Research Journal*, Vol.16, No. 1, pp. 45–61.